

A Study on Consumers' Online Purchase Intentions of Groceries through Mobile Applications

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Abstract

Online shopping is a revolution in consumer markets as it can provide a convenient shopping experience to the customers. It offers lot of benefits to the customers in the form of time, cost and utility. It has extended its presence from offering electronic products to daily necessities. One of such offerings are groceries.

As the groceries are daily necessities to the customers, they have many questions in their mind about buying groceries online. In the changing world of buyer's market, identifying the needs and wants of the customers and understanding the consumer attitude is the challenging task.

Online grocery shopping has been noted of being a relatively young but promising area of electronic commerce. However, only a sparse number of studies have been focusing on consumers' intentions to purchase grocery products online in the cross-cultural context.

There is a need to explore the buying intentions of customers to buy groceries online. The present study will explore the purchase intentions of customers while they purchase groceries online.

The present study was based on available literature on online shopping of groceries and understanding customer attitude towards it. The main objective of the study is to determine the customer perception towards online grocery shopping.

Keywords: Buying intentions, online shopping of groceries, customer perception, and electronic commerce.

Introduction

The revolution of internet has far reaching impact on the online retail business in India. The growth of usage of internet by the users made them to find more convenient ways to shop online. The number of customers buying products and services online is also growing for the last few years. The most common products purchased online are textile, electronic products, and footwear and beauty products. In the recent years there is a considerable change in variety of products purchased online by the consumers.

The variety of products range from furniture to automobile, accessories to spares and staple food to groceries. There is change in the lifestyle of the consumers, which made buying decisions to change.

Increase in number of nuclear families, changing consumption habits, increase in disposable income, and change in profile of husband and wife and busy life style lead to switching from traditional buying of daily necessities to online shopping. Groceries is not exception to the consumers in urban areas.

Due to various benefits like ease to shop, comparison of products, price discounts, more variety of products, easy to place order, door delivery, cash on delivery and reviews on performance of the products, the consumers are preferring to shop groceries online with the help of website and applications (Farida Khan 2015).

Even though there is a trend towards online buying of groceries, but still there are concerns about online shopping like, food safety, hygiene, payment risk, return risk etc. Besides, in order to increase consumer’s trust, food retailers should also proactively provide accurate and sufficient information about their food products online (Anh Kim Dang et. al. 2018).

Review of Literature

The consumers buy groceries online mainly because of offers and discounts, variety of product available, free home delivery, website user friendliness and cash of delivery payment option. Purchasing unique and special items and best price offered are another reasons for buying groceries online and demographic variables, such as gender, age group don’t have influence of the factors of customer satisfaction (S.Sathyaraj et.al. 2015).

Even though there is an explosion of internet and mobile technology, most of the consumers still prefer the conventional way of shopping of groceries. Awareness and accessibility are two major challenges for growth of online grocery retailing in India which need to be handle properly (Snehal Chincholkar 2016).

The flexibility, anywhere and anytime to buy the products, less time taken to search for products, comparison of products and availability of information are the reasons for consumers to prefer online shopping of groceries. Delay in delivery, risks in payment, lack of privacy etc. are some of the reasons for disliking the online shopping (Zetty Madina Md. Zaini et.al. 2011).

Some of the housewives and employed females prefer to buy groceries from general stores in spite of online grocery provides convenience, ease, privacy and saves time. They prefer to groceries online from reputed online sellers due to time saving and ease of ordering (Krunal K. Punjani 2017).

Most of the customers prefer to buy groceries are women than men. Most common reasons to shop groceries online are saving of time and effort, on average customers for this model are satisfied with the quality of the products received by them, also the sellers are providing customers with option of replacement. The expectation of a customer while buying groceries online and in physical market is totally different (Himanshu et.al. 2016).

Most of the consumers shopping online are young and they purchase the groceries on monthly basis. While purchasing online the customers were able to compare the rates and number and type of variants available on other online grocery shopping platforms which gave them an assurance that the purchase they were doing was worth their money (Mariam Saleem et.al. 2018).

Behavioural intentions and attitude of consumers while they shop online are influenced by perceived behavioural control, knowledge and ability to buy groceries online and ease of buying. The attitude of consumers will positively influence the consumer’s intentions to shop groceries online (Amol Ranadive 2015).

Objectives of the study

This research is undertaken the following objectives

- To study the purchase intentions of consumers of groceries online with help of mobile applications.
- To study the attributes that influences the consumers' purchase intentions of groceries online.

Research Methodology

The present study aims at understanding purchase intentions of consumers of groceries online with help of mobile applications and identifying attributes that influences the consumers' purchase intentions of groceries online.

The study was based on previous works done by researchers in the area of online shopping of groceries. Review of available literature was done and gap areas were identified. The study was purely based on secondary available about online shopping.

While consumers shop online, their level of awareness about online shopping is a crucial factor which determines the consumer decision making. Awareness about modes of accessing online shopping, searching for products and buying products.

As the consumers aware of online shopping, they tend to go to websites to search for products and services to buy them. Consumer decision making is the critical stage in online shopping and it can be influenced by various factors.

Discussions

The consumers are aware of their purchase intentions towards online shopping of groceries in the country. The common intentions to purchase groceries online are ease of shopping, price benefit, door delivery, price and product comparison, flexibility in shopping, scheduling of delivery etc.

They are few concerns along with benefits in online shopping of groceries. The major concerns are privacy, financial risks, return policy, virtual carts, trust among people who deliver groceries and saving time.

Most of the studies revealed that even though there is shift towards online shopping of groceries, most of the people still prefer to shop in the traditional way as the awareness an accessibility are less in the market.

According to changing trend, the customers who buy groceries are focusing to maximise their benefits in online shopping. Many efforts are being made by the customers to optimize their presence in the digital world. As the competition is becoming intense online the online retailers are now able to offer different variety of fresh and packaged food items, which can be easily transported and delivered to the customers.

The trend may change further in the future as the online retailers can offer more convenient services to the customers as they tend to buy products more online. Mobile applications will also play a significant role in bringing groceries online so close to the customers.

Conclusion

Though online grocery shopping is not for everyone, but there is a growth in the digital presence of customers. This trend may continue in the future with the help of mobile applications, which can provide a convenient shopping. Online retailers must understand the needs of customers of groceries and make their products available online. Making mobile applications user friendly, providing more variety of products, building the confidence among customers about online shopping and providing the additional benefits might bring more online grocers. Making it a smooth, simple

and seamless online experience is key. The online retailers should focus on service quality and delivery should be improved. The websites and applications need to be more dynamic to make the online grocery shopping experience easier, more stimulating and rewarding for customers. This is very important, as it suggests that the decision to shop online is frequently re-evaluated, creating tangible opportunities for conversion by online providers. E-grocery providers should also monitor use frequency identifying drop outs and actively targeting them with promotional offers.

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